

Re-inventing a Model for Rural Information Services for an Inclusive Information Society in Nigeria: The Role of Rural and Community Libraries and Information Centres

Onyemachi, M. C. (onyemachichibueze@yahoo.com)

Ahmed A. Ayandokun (ahmedabayandokun@gmail.com)

**Department of Library and Information Science, Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana,
Ebonyi State, Nigeria**

Paper presented at the Conference/AGM of the Nigerian Library Association, Anambra Chapter.

Date: 30th November – 1st December, 2022.

Theme: Library Engagements for Sustainable Digital Society

Abstract

This article focuses on the creation of a model for the delivery of information services to influence the attainment of an inclusive information society using rural and community libraries. The paper uses current empirical and non-empirical documentary sources to explain the concepts of rural community, information society and sustainable development. It also describes rural and community libraries and information centres as those societal institutions that provide information to the grassroots and rural dwellers basically targeting their specific information needs. It outlines the important roles of the rural and community libraries and information centres in achieving sustainable development through inclusivity under the areas of bridging the digital divide and having direct interaction with the rural populace in a two-way framework involving action and feedbacks. An 8-point model information services for an inclusive information society is drafted to include information for political inclusion, financial/economic inclusion, educational/literacy inclusion, socio-cultural inclusion, among others. The challenges and prospects of implementing rural information services for an inclusive information society include poor information infrastructure and architecture, inadequate policies on rural information services, government negligence of the rural communities, etc. The paper recommends creation of policies on rural information services delivery, training of librarians on contemporary rural information services delivery, provision of adequate modern rural information infrastructure and architecture and other means of addressing the challenges identified.

Keywords: Model, rural information services, inclusive information society, rural libraries, community libraries, Information Centres

Introduction

Societies are systems with subsystems, and their collective welfare is built upon the aggregate welfare of the average member. The higher the percentage of members whose needs are met, the higher the indices of societal development. An uneven society is one with uneven distribution of human and material resources and services. The imbalance that may arise from such an uneven distribution of resources and services is a perfect recipe for socio-political and economic instability with devastating effects. Information is one of such major resources, and in the 21st century, information occupies a central place as a major resource for development because of its role in enhancing result-oriented decision making among individuals and groups.

Information is described as a commodity for development; a processed data to which meaning may be attached; useful for planning, decision making and reduction of uncertainty (Oluwaseyi, Akanni, & Busuyi, 2017). Jimoh (2011) explains that information is considered the oil that greases the society, a veritable tool and resource for result-oriented planning, decision-making and implementation among individuals, organizations, governments and the global society. According to Osuigwe and Unagha (2018), access to information has been adjudged as a necessity and a major factor in the development and empowerment of the citizenry of any society in achieving economic, political and educational successes.

Meanwhile, the information society entails a *society* characterized by rapid *growth and use of information*, widespread exploitation of varied *information sources*; a society where people *know and appreciate* what information they *need*, *where* to get it, *how* to get the information, and in the end, *how to use* it (Michael, as cited in Jeremiah, n.d). Isachenko (2018) notes that with the formation of the information society, an information and communication and economic space was formed that transformed information into one of the most important resources for the development of society. The concept of information society has come to be known as a society where the average member appreciates the value of, have access to, and can use information to attain personal and collective goals and objectives.

Yadav (2017), states that information is power and a vital source for human beings for living a prosperous life on the earth. Information is all around and is utilized in all walks of life. Thus the information helps against social imbalance. It is the supreme asset than all other movable and immovable asset that the people hold on earth. In the contemporary world people are valued as rich and poor not because of their assets; but they are valued as information rich and information poor. Similarly, information plays a very important role among rural people.

Rural communities are communities that are often disadvantaged in terms of access to urban social amenities and facilities that make life easier and worthwhile. They include communities with fewer inhabitants and socio-economic opportunities, especially in a developing country like Nigeria. According to Nwokocha and Chimah (2016), the African population is still predominantly illiterates and rural dwellers. Nigeria rural population for 2019 was 98,156,653, a 0.92% increase from 2018 (Macrotrends, 2021). This accounts for about 48.04% of the country's over 200 million estimated population. They are usually affected by an evident lack and inadequate public social amenities for the citizenry. Utor and Utor (2006) state that the characteristics of rural dwellers include low level of literacy or high level of illiteracy; limited educational and economic (including jobs opportunities); strong cultural, tribal and religious adherence; absence of large business and commercial institutions; and limited social facilities e.g. electricity supply, educational institutions and communication system among others. As such, they are vulnerable and often disadvantaged. This lack of inclusion creates a loophole for instability that may stem from a combination of one or more of rural urban migration, overpopulation in cities, poor education, exploitation of natural resources, illegal migration, environmental degradation, kidnapping, banditry among other societal menace.

The development that access to, and use of information provides for any society cannot be over-emphasized. Libraries and information centres, especially rural libraries and information centres have become integral aspect of man's society in providing information services to drive the goals of man. Unfortunately, just like every other resource, there is an evident divide among the privileged and less privileged societies when it comes to access to information and information resources. Rural communities, far flung

from the reach of basic social amenities and information infrastructure are often deprived of the potentials and advantages that having access to and being able to use information in making informed socio-economic individual and communal decisions offer.

Public libraries and information centres, especially the rural ones provide an opportunity for a balanced society because they are the information institutions that do not discriminate in their delivery of information services. The relationship with the concept of public library can be found, among other aspects, in that the library is an inclusive institution, because its activities are destined to favour all citizens without distinctions of age, race, sex, religion, nationality (Talavera-Ibarra, & Vega, 2015). A functioning public sphere is one of the essential preconditions of any democracy, and the libraries have served as an institution underpinning a sustainable public sphere by being providers of knowledge and cultural expressions, being agents fostering an enlightened and informed citizenry, and being arenas for public debate (Audunson, Aabø, Blomgren, Evjen, Jochumsen, Larsen, Rasmussen, Vårheim, Johnston, Koizumi, 2019).

It is expected that an inclusive society that guarantees the participation and satisfaction of the needs of all societal groups and members can only be achieved if the access to information, and its use are optimized. This paper therefore seeks to prepare a model for re-inventing the delivery of rural information resources and services in Nigeria, using public rural and community libraries, with the final objective of contributing to the creation of an inclusive society that will help address in the long run, some of the major crises that have bedeviled not just the rural communities, but their closer urban relatives and the general society as a whole in Nigeria and similar societies.

The Rural Community

A rural area is an open swath of land that has few homes or other buildings, and not very many people. A rural area's population density is very low (National Geographic Society, 2022). A lot of factors are considered in characterizing a community as rural. Such features may be based on population, demographics of inhabitants, economic value, distance from urban centres, access to social amenities and infrastructural facilities, geographical isolation and land mass, among others. However, according to Ford and

Cheprasov (2022) the economic value of rural areas is largely based on the natural resources available to people, and the monetization of those natural resources. This determines the type of work available in a community, and people living in rural communities are often specialists in their type of work. The economies of rural communities largely rely on either agriculture, mining, manufacturing, recreation (tourism), culture, or are dependent economically on the local, state or federal government. A large portion of rural communities is unspecialized, which usually means the area depends on a variety of economic categories.

Rural areas tend to share higher rates of poverty, unemployment and underemployment, and uninsured and underinsured compared to urban areas (Curtis, & Cohn, 2015). According to Anie (2014), rural communities in Nigeria is characterized by the economically backward areas-villages typified and handicapped by poverty, high illiteracy rate, unemployment, subsistence economy, and lack of economic and social amenities such as roads, electricity, pipe-born water, hospitals, banks, industries, rural telephony, etc.

The Information Society and its importance

The term information society has been proposed to refer to the post-industrial society in which information plays a pivotal role (Nath, 2009). The knowledge economy and the digital economy are some of the unique characteristic features of the information society. This means that a unanimous and universal acknowledgment of information as a factor of production has emphasised the quality that information brings to those who possess it alongside knowledge, and subsequently, gives them the competitive advantage over those who do not. The digital economy also underlines the recognition of the roles that modern information and communication technologies play in the creation of access to, management and efficient use of information to drive socio-economic and political development and transform societies (Ayandokun, & Nworu, 2022).

“A characteristic feature of the modern information society is the growth of knowledge, the transformation of information into the main subject of human labour. Today, it can be confidently stated that in the era of information technology and high-tech production, information production becomes one of the types of manufacturing industry, and science becomes a productive force. Information society is based on information and a well-developed network of services. This has affected all spheres of society: education, health, cultural institutions, whose members either receive or provide information, transferring their knowledge as a service. Rapid development of Internet technologies has opened new ways of organizing business relations at different levels. Through the Internet and web technologies, new ways of financial calculations, electronic payments appeared, as well as the ability to make purchases, receive various services. Information and communication technologies are used as a means of intercultural communication, which has broadened the opportunities for citizens to communicate with each other throughout our planet on forums, websites, and blogs.”

(Isachenko, 2018).

As a result of the value that information brings to the society, it is now regarded as a vital aspect of human development that must be equally and evenly distributed. It is the only commodity that one can sell and still have, yet most economists and other researchers agree that information-and communication-related activities account for an unprecedented proportion of economic investment and output in wealthy societies (Encyclopedia of Communication and Information, 2019). The phenomenon being referred to as the global information society is a fundamental change that is unfolding before us is that action is taking place within the context of a society that is global and increasingly relies on information accessed through technologies (Qureshi, 2006).

Inclusivity as a means of Sustainable Societal Development

The Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations (2016) defines inclusion or social inclusion as the process of improving the terms of participation in society for people who are disadvantaged on the basis of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion, or economic or other status, through enhanced opportunities, access to resources, voice and respect for rights. It is as much a process as it is a goal, the objective of which is to erase its direct opposite, social exclusion.

Exclusion expands social cleavages and widens social fissures thereby increasing the threats of drifting towards socio-political instability. Sustainable development cannot be attained in the absence of inclusion. Members of the society must be well accommodated if the society must attain sustainable socio-economic development. Inclusion has become an integral aspect of global development plan so much that several governmental and non-governmental organisations have factored it into their short and long term plans. For instance, it is the Goal 16 of the United Nations 17 Sustainable Development Goals, which reads to *“Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.”* (Conference of European National Librarians, 2022).

Rural and Community Libraries and Information Centres

Rural libraries are locally based service organizations established to meet the requirements of the local communities and to function within the context of the communities while contributing to the creation and maintenance of a well informed and democratic society. In the development of rural areas, rural libraries play pivotal roles in the welfare of the rural masses by acting as community information centre to improve living condition and quality of life by fulfilling each and every information need, those which assist individuals in their day to day problem-solving (Kumbar, & lamani, 2014).

Community Information Centres (CICs) are information centres Community information centres are libraries domiciled in economically disadvantaged communities to meet the information needs of the isolated rural dwellers, more importantly by providing them with information that will aid hands-on and inventive results in their various kinds of

production (Uzuegbu, & Uzuegbu, 2014). They are also described as those centres and institutions that assist individuals and groups with daily problem-solving information and with participation in the democratic process. These services focus on the needs of people those who do not have ready access to other sources of assistance and on the most important problems that concern their day to day activities in their homes, with job opportunities and their rights (Kumbar, & lamani, 2014).

Rural libraries and community information centres can therefore be said to have interwoven functions. While the rural libraries are tailored towards delivering library services to the identified isolated communities, the community information services centres offer extensive services exceeding ordinary library services, but including providing a meeting point for community members to interact, engage in community development discourse members of the community and government, acquire competencies and skills, and partake in activities that give them sense of belonging.

Important Roles of the Rural and Community Libraries and Information Centres in Achieving Sustainable Development through Inclusivity

If information is the principal resource or commodity in an information society, then equitable access to information technologies, information infrastructure, information resources and services is crucial if that society is to be a fair and just one that will attain its developmental goals (Encyclopedia of Communication and Information, 2019). Failure to do this will widen the digital divide and create further imbalances between those with the privileges and those without them due to economic and social factors such as race, income, family structure, literacy, national or regional origin, or other factors. The introduction and existence of a new communication medium and the emergence of advanced but expensive telecommunication media can further create an information gap between the best-positioned members of a society and the less fortunate, thereby excluding many people from educational, political, social, physical, geographical and economic opportunities.

The very existence of the “digital divide”—or lack of access to information and communication technology (ICT) for certain segments of the population—exacerbates inequalities (Servon, 2002). At the same time ICT can bring education to people, healthcare

to disadvantaged communities, and promote civic engagement and better management of natural resources (Qureshi, 2006). Unfortunately, there is a missing link because in rural communities in developing countries like Nigeria, there is an evident digital divide between the economically buoyant and the economically disadvantaged. This is where rural and community libraries come in for disadvantaged communities.

Libraries based on social inclusion are libraries that facilitate communities to develop their potential by viewing cultural diversity, willingness to accept change, and offering opportunities to strive for, protect and advocate culture and human rights (Wiyono, 2021). Marwiah (2019) indicates that shared public information and increased accessibility of the community's activities will remove a feeling of exclusion and with adequate information, members of a society will have opportunity to participate in community activities and enable them to be more well-informed people thereby contributing to societal development. Rural library and information centres could play a significant role in the socio-economic development of rural areas by providing information and communication services to the rural people (Hoq, 2014).

Several examples abound in the developed societies of the roles libraries, especially public and community libraries underlining the roles libraries can play in ensuring inclusion. Unfortunately, the case is far from it in the Nigerian context. For instance, in the case of three Peru public libraries which have successfully executed the inclusion programmes in public libraries, Talavera-Ibarra and Vega (2015) state that the libraries offer a variety of services for population of all ages and social conditions, particularly in non-traditional places such as parks, beaches, churches, homes, and work areas. For example, since 2011 there are information and recreational literature services for adults and children on the beaches (3500 books loaned in summer, from December to March). Since 2012 it is possible to borrow on Sunday books, newspapers, videos and magazines for children and adults in two churches. There is daily reading for children, and materials for parents in the Kennedy park (in the district center). For young people, there is literature, comics, music, videos and other. And public schools in the district are visited once a week (about 500 books are borrowed every year). These centres, referred to as *bibliotecas rurales*, have developed into educational and cultural movements that

incorporate literacy activities, local language publications, reading and learning (Ortiz, as cited in Ndinde, 2014).

The Community Information Centre offers vital inclusive roles such as:

- Provision of information and activities which will help community members acquire the skills, knowledge and confidence to participate more fully in community affairs,
- Provision of information and activities about health and agricultural techniques, business etc, to assist community to improve their economic situation,
- Provision of a forum through which governments and other agency workers can be informed about concerns, problems and reactions of community members to their plans and programmes,
- Provision of support to extension programmes and helping extension workers to co-ordinate their work in the community,
- Strengthening a community's involvement in and appreciation of local and national culture,
- Serving as a focal point for community's activities and enhancing a sense of belonging among community members.

(Kumbar, & Lamani, 2014).

In particular, equity of access is part of this core principle of libraries' social justice and welfare provision (Abdullahi, 2015; Pereyaslavskaya, & Abba, 2015). Public libraries can serve as advocates for social justice, as well as promoters of human dignity and of ***sustainable development*** activities. In this view, public librarians are seen as having the responsibility to treat information services for social welfare as a fundamental aspect of their current services (Racelis, 2018).

Rural and community libraries offer unique advantages over all other forms of libraries as far as inclusion is concerned:

- i. *Two-way framework*: Rural and community libraries and information centres perform more interactive role with feedback features that guarantee the libraries the opportunity to obtain vital data that will help them serve the users

- better. This feature becomes easier because the rural libraries and information centres offer services that are more group specific than other libraries. The information services rendered are tailored towards specific needs of the users based on the results of the community analysis done with the user profile.
- ii. *Bridging the digital divide:* The disadvantaged position of rural dwellers excludes them from digital participation. And in a developing country like Nigeria, the gap is further widened by an evident infrastructural decay in terms of power generation, transmission and distribution which is still below global standards even among the urban communities. Therefore, the rural libraries and information centres can offer the services that can help bridge the digital divide through the provision of services such as internet and audio-visual devices that will connect the rural populace to the rest of the world and make them feel included.
 - iii. *Rural Enlightenment:* Rural enlightenment is the product that is bound to occur when the rural populace is provided with educative and sensitizing information services directly tailored towards their basic and long-term needs. The need to make informed socio-economic decisions is as important for the rural citizen as it is for the urban citizen. Therefore, the rural community library and information centre occupies a central place in delivering the services targeted at.

Re-Inventing a Model Information Services for an Inclusive Information Society in Nigeria

Exclusion creates several societal imbalances and therefore, must be addressed from all angles. The public libraries need to be repositioned and re-engineered to render effective information services to the socially excluded people in their communities and in the society (Igiomoh, & Ogunwemimo, 2013). The urgency for public librarians to ensure social inclusion to their services, as well as for them to contribute to society's efforts to address social exclusion, cannot be questioned and they should really address all primary needs that can be linked to information needs and access to information (Fuorie, 2007).

Chelliah (2014) supported the proposition of a model for sustainable library services in a multicultural context built upon input, actions and outcomes, the most important element being surveying the community profile. However, this paper presents an 8-point model tailored towards the average Nigerian society, with emphasis on the specific roles expected of a library and information centre targeting inclusion.

- i. *Educational/Literacy inclusion role:* Education and enlightenment are the principal roles of public libraries all over the world. For a populace having deficient educational infrastructure, the rural populace will have the rural library and information centres as buffers to provide succour in terms educational services such as mass literacy, adult education, children information services, research and development, among others. This provides an opportunity for the academically excluded to be well informed. In a knowledge-driven economy, only those with basic education, formally, semi-formally, or informally acquired will be able to participate effectively in the society and maximize collective and individual potentials.
- ii. *Agro-Food security inclusion role:* Food sustenance is very vital to human survival, and as rural dwellers in Nigeria are often immersed in subsistence and commercial scale farming, there is a need to engage rural community members in agricultural information services delivery. This will help in providing information on crop management, planting practices, agricultural raw materials sales, purchase and marketing, extension services, agricultural facilities access.
- iii. *Digital inclusion role:* There is a massive gap, a huge crater of digital divide exists between the urban dwellers and the rural dwellers. The rural community library and information centres can help provide the access to digital literacy and digital devices in order to bridge the digital divide existing between the information privileged and the digitally excluded. Teaching of digital literacy is expected to be part of this project because even with access to resources, only the digitally literate can maximize the potentials of the digital economy and be fully integrated into the digital economy as active participants.

- iv. *Democratic/Political inclusion role:* The democratic participation of the politically excluded can be enhanced through the provision of political information services such as information on political activities like voter registration, bulletins and other Current Awareness Services on political events, public debates, engagements with political stakeholders, democratic participation advocacy. Town hall meetings with politicians, display of voters list, voter education, etc are some of the non-conventional information services that rural community libraries and information centres can incorporate into their services to integrate the politically excluded citizenry into the political sphere.
- v. *Socio-cultural inclusion role:* The rural community library and information centre is better positioned than any other social institution to deliver services targeted at cultural preservation. The cultural activities and heritage of the indigenous rural community dwellers are at the door step of the rural librarian. Therefore, efforts should be made to collect and preserve indigenous knowledge in various areas of indigenous practices such as local administration, public health protection, environmental protection, ecology, security, agriculture, tradition and customs, family life, communal lifestyle, tourism, recreation, entertainment, etc. Apart from preserving the cultural practices for posterity purposes, this can also provide an opportunity for the rural community library to engage the outside world and provide the publicity needed to attract tourism and investment to rural communities. When vital information that shows the potentials of the rural community in the areas listed under this point are made available to the larger society through publications by the library and exhibition via websites, it provides prospects of attraction, thereby enhancing inclusion for community members and the community as a whole.
- vi. *Medico-health inclusion role:* Health is wealth, they say. But health is bigger than wealth. It is life itself. To maintain a balanced level of human productivity that can support societal development, members of the society must be well informed on medical and health related issues. The rural community libraries and information centres should provide timely, accurate, and reliable information on epidemics and pandemics, emergency public health crises in the community and the society at

large, maternal and infant health, public health, among others in order to sustain the productivity level of the rural community. The physically challenged, mentally challenged with psychomotor challenges must have adequate services and resources that can provide information to them in the easiest manner.

- vii. *Occupational inclusion role:* Rural community library and information centres can provide supportive occupational information from newspaper adverts, resume and CV preparation, career advisory services, job training, online job searching, job application assistant, test preparation, cover letter development, referrals to training, small business development, interview practice, among others.
- viii. *Financial-economic inclusion role:* This role is performed to assist library users with access to financial facilities and financial literacy education. Urban libraries in advanced countries have been providing financial literacy programmes for their users, in collaboration with financial and security institutions like banks and insurance companies.

One major factor that must not be disregarded is the inclusion of the physically challenged in all these programmes. The library services must be designed in such a way that resources that cater for the visually impaired, those with hearing impairments, those who psychomotor and physiological challenges are used.

8-point Model for Rural Information Services for an Inclusive Information Society in Nigeria (Source: Authors).

Challenges and Prospects of Implementing Rural Information Services for an Inclusive Information Society in Rural Areas

That rural library and information centres play vital roles in societal development is no longer debatable, the question, especially in developing societies like Nigeria is if they are able to play the roles they are established to play as expected. This question arises from several factors. In most parts of the world, especially in the developing countries, these centres are plagued with various problems like insufficient funds, lack of government and community support, uncertainty about sustainability, etc (Hoq, 2014). This is corroborated by Uzuegbu and Uzuegbu (2013) who note that the type of services expected of rural and community libraries and information centres do not exist in Nigeria and has got to begin since the present information services of public libraries has failed to include the rural communities. The factors responsible for these anomalies are not far-fetched. They include poor funding, lack of recognition of the importance and roles of community libraries, total absence of community libraries and information centres in several areas, inadequate staff in public libraries, poor recognition of the importance of

public libraries by state and local governments, and absence of critical information infrastructure.

Igwe and Onah (2013) identify lack of relevant government policies for overall library development, poor state of existing libraries and information centres, inadequacy of human resources, infrastructural facilities and information resources in existing libraries, passive library and information professionals who are reluctant to move with the contemporary trends as challenges of library and information services development in Nigeria. Similarly, Sadiku, Olarongbe & Tsafe (2018) iterate that challenges of public libraries in Nigeria which hinder the delivery of its programmes include inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, inadequate human resources and dependence on government for support. This is similar to the findings of Umoh, Habib and Yusuf (2018) which indicate that public library services are militated by poor infrastructure, inadequate funding, and inadequate staffing, among others. These have direct impacts on the delivery of outreach services to the community in which public libraries belong. Many of these are in relation to inadequate or limited resources. They include limited or inconsistent internet connectivity, lack of suitable venues to deliver programmes, reduced budgets and staff shortages. The public library system in Nigeria suffers a variety of challenges, including neglect, lack of recognition, inadequate funding and personnel, all of which have adversely affected its services provision (Saka, 2019).

One major challenge of public library services to rural dwellers has been the issue of legislation and political will by owners of rural libraries and information centres, the government. According to Awogbami, Opele, & Adeyemi, (2018) the challenges of information service provision by library boards include lack of appropriate laws and policies governing the public library system, inappropriate government support, funding issues, lack of efficient library management and staffing issues. This often occurs because several Nigerian public libraries are rarely decentralized to local levels. This often creates distance and a wide gap between the urban users and the potential users from the rural communities, leading to information services exclusion.

Conclusion and Recommendation

An imbalanced society, occasioned by exclusion of integral members of the society is a recipe for social instability and underdevelopment. Providing access to information to cover marginalised and information-deprived populace can help enhance sustainable development. Inclusion guarantees a sense of belonging and capacity enhancement thereby improving social capital and the subsequently development. Information services to rural dwellers, who are often geographically, economically and socially disadvantaged is paramount to societal development, and no other social institution than the rural community libraries and information centres can offer this buffer. An 8-point target model, designed to enhance socio-cultural, educational, medical, agricultural, political, occupational, economic, and digital inclusion has been provided to enhance an even/inclusive sustainable socio-economic development for the rural community, which in turn will improve societal development at large.

Unfortunately, some hindrances such a poor funding, staffing challenges, infrastructural decay and government negligence have limited and prevented the delivery of inclusive information services. These challenges must be addressed by the stakeholders involved in the delivery of rural library and information services if an inclusive information society must be achieved. The following recommendations are hereby put forward to address the anomalies:

- i. Provision of funds for the construction of rural and community libraries and information centres. This will help provide the needed opportunity for the dwellers to have access to developmental information. These funds will also cater for the procurement of adequate modern digital technologies to enhance digital inclusion. This is traditionally a role that the government must wake up to even in the midst of economic downturn. Government can engage the private sector in raising funds through the use of Public-Private Partnership.
- ii. Training and retraining of library and information professionals in practice and in library schools to acquire modern inclusive information practice because of the peculiarities of the inclusive information services.

- iii. Enactment of strong implementable policy on inclusive information services based on extant laws for inclusivity and included in the duties of public library boards.
- iv. Synergy with other professionals that will facilitate inclusivity. This includes professionals with specialties in specific areas such as health, agriculture and food security, education, economics and finance, among others. This will help improve the impact of the inclusion drive programmes of the library.

References

- Abdullahi, J. (2015). Policy framework on social welfare information management and services for Nigerian public libraries. *Library Management*, 36(4/5), 281-288. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-08-2014-0088>
- Anie S. O. (2014). Improving public library services for rural community development. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management* 5 (2), 203 – 210.
- Audunson, R., Aabø, S., Blomgren, R., Evjen, S., Jochumsen, H., Larsen, H., Rasmussen, C. H., Vårheim, A., Johnston, J., Koizumi, M. (2019). Public libraries as an infrastructure for a sustainable public sphere: A comprehensive review of research. *Journal of Documentation*. <https://munin.uit.no/bitstream/handle/10037/17847/article.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y>
- Awogbami, P. A., Opele, J. K., & Adeyemi, F. C. (2021) investigated “a scoping review of the functions of library board in ensuring information service provision in Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews* 11 (1), 181 – 188. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351942803_A_SCOPING_REVIEW_OF_THE_FUNCTIONS_OF_LIBRARY_BOARD_IN_ENSUREING_INFORMATION_SERVICE_PROVISION_IN_LAGOS_STATE_NIGERIA/link/60b287ef299bf1f6d5848aa6/download
- Ayandokun, A. A., & Nworu, C. N. (2022). *Innovative information repackaging strategies in public libraries for the sustainable development of grassroots and the vulnerable in the knowledge and digital economy*. Paper presented at the 60th AGM and National Conference of the Nigerian Library Association, Abuja, Sunday, 3rd July – Friday, 8th July, 2022 at the Boston Even Centre.
- Curtis, L., & Cohn, T. J. (2015). Overview of rural communities: Context and challenges. *Psychology and Aids Exchange Newsletter*. American Psychological Association. <https://www.apa.org/pi/aids/resources/exchange/2015/01/rural-communities>
- Ford, A., & Cheprasov, A. (2022). Rural community characteristics and examples. Study.com <https://study.com/learn/lesson/rural-community-characteristics-examples.html>
- Fuorie, I. (2007). Public libraries addressing social inclusion: how we may think...World Library and Information Conference. 73RD IFLA GENERAL CONFERENCE AND COUNCIL 19-23 August 2007, Durban, South Africa. [https://repository.up.ac.za/bitstream/handle/2263/3542/fourie_theoretical\(2007\).pdf;sequence=1](https://repository.up.ac.za/bitstream/handle/2263/3542/fourie_theoretical(2007).pdf;sequence=1)

- Chelliah, R., (2014). Community building, multiculturalism and the suburban public library. Doctor of Philosophy and Information Science. Edith Cowan University. <http://ro.ecu.edu.au/theses/1524/>
- Conference of European National Librarians (2022). IFLA: Libraries, Development and the United Nations 2030 Agenda. <https://www.cenl.org/ifla-libraries-development-and-the-united-nations-2030-agenda/>
- The Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations (2016). Identifying social inclusion and exclusion. Leaving no one behind: The imperative of inclusive development. Report on the World Social Situation 2016. <https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/rwss/2016/chapter1.pdf>
- Hoq, K. M. G. (2014). Rural library and information services, their success, failure and sustainability: A literature review. *Information Development* 31 (3), 294 – 310. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0266666913515693?journalCode=idva>
- Igwe, K. N. & Onah, E. A. (2013). Issues and concerns in the service deliberately system of libraries to users in the globalization era. In A. O. Issa, K. N. Igwe, & C. P. Uzuegbu (Eds), *Provision of Library and Information Services to Users in the era of Globalisation*. [pp. 20-41]. Lagos, Nigeria: Waltodany Visual Concept
- Information Society, Description of. (2019). In *Encyclopedia of Communication and Information*. Encyclopedia.com: <https://www.encyclopedia.com/media/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/information-society-description>
- Igiamoh, V. E., & Ogunwemimo, A. O. (2013). Re-positioning public libraries in Nigeria for social inclusion services. *World Libraries*. <https://worldlibraries.dom.edu/index.php/worldlib/article/view/486/469>
- Isachenko, (2018). The role of information and informational and communication technologies in modern society. *Utopía y Praxis Latinoamericana* 23 (82), 361 – 367. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/279/27957591031/27957591031.pdf>
- Jeremiah, O. O. (n.d). IRMA: Introduction to information science. http://www.babcock.edu.ng/oer/lecture_notes/irm/IRMA%20102.3.ppt
- Jimoh, R. A. (2011). An overview of information and communication technology (ICT) systems for library services. In R. A. Jimoh, & K. N. Igwe (Eds), *Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Systems for Library Services*. [pp. 1 – 5]. Offa, Nigeria: Wunmi Commercial Press.

- Kumbar, B. D., & Lamani, M. B. (2014). Rural libraries as community information centre: A study of Karnataka State. *E-Library Science Research Journal* 2 (11), 1 – 5.
- Macrotrends (2021). Nigeria rural population 1960-2021. <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/NGA/nigeria/rural-population#:~:text=Nigeria%20rural%20population%20for%202020,a%200.92%25%20increase%20from%202018>
- Marwiah, P. (2019). Social inclusion for older people through library services. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research* 302, 127 - 131. *2nd International Conference on Culture and Language in Southeast Asia (ICCLAS 2018)*. <https://www.atlantispress.com/article/55913029.pdf>
- Nath, H. K. (2009). The information society. *SIBCOLTEJO – A Journal of the SCTU*, 4, 19 – 29. https://www.shsu.edu/eco_hkn/The%20Information%20Society.pdf
- National Geographic Society (2022). *Rural area*. <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/rural-area>
- Ndinde, S. (2014). The Role of Community Based Information Centres in Development: Lessons for Rural Zimbabwe. *Developing Country Studies* 4 (19), 107 – 111. <https://iiste.org/Journals/index.php/DCS/article/download/16057/16183>
- Nwokocha, U., & Chimah, J. N. (2016) *Library and information services for rural community development in Africa: Problems and prospects*. Paper presented at: IFLA WLIC 2016 – Columbus, OH – Connections. Collaboration. Community in Session S27 - Africa. In Building Cross Cultural Capacities for Universal Access to Information and Knowledge in Africa, 11-12 August 2016, Athens, Ohio, USA. <http://library.ifla.org/id/eprint/2081/1/S27-2016-nwokocha-en.pdf>
- Oluwaseye, A. J., Akanni, M. J., & Busuyi, A. O. (2017). Information needs, and seeking behaviour of medical students at College of Medicine, University of Ibadan. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology* 10 (2), 48 – 62.
- Osuigwe, N., & Unagha, A. O. (2018). Public libraries today: Resources, services, challenges and prospects. In A. O. Unagha, & K. N. Igwe (eds), *Anatomy of Libraries and Information Centres*. (pp. 51 – 67). Lagos, Nigeria: Zeh Communications.
- Pereyaslavskaya, K. & Abba, C. (2015). Don't be a reference "tool": How to use internal marketing to build staff competencies in the age of inclusive libraries. *Reference & User Services Quarterly*, 55(2), 102-108. <https://doi.org/10.5860/rusq.55n2.102>
- Qureshi, S. (2006). Why is the information society important to us? *The World Summit on the Information Society in Tunis*. (Editorial Introduction). 12 (1), 1-5. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/itdj.20035>
- Racelis, A. (2018). Library services for the poor: Theoretical framework for library social responsibility. *Pedagogical Research*, 3(2), 06. <https://doi.org/10.20897/pr/90831>

- Sadiku, S. A. Olarongbe, S.A., & Tsafe, A.G. (2018). Public libraries: Conceptual explanation, historical development, functions and organizational structure. In A. O. Unagha & K. N. Igwe (Eds), *Anatomy of Libraries and Information Centres*. [pp. 40-50]. Lagos, Nigeria: Zeh Communication
- Saka, K. A. (2019). *Public library services for a truly democratic Nigeria*. A Paper Presented at the 57th National Conference/AGM of the Nigerian Library Association Held at the Petroleum Training Institute (PTI) Conference Centre, Efurrun-Warri Delta State, Nigeria From 28th July – 2nd August, 2019.
- Servon, L. (2002). *Bridging the digital divide: Technology, community, and public policy*. Malden, MA & Oxford: Blackwell Publishing
- Talavera-Ibarra, A. M., & Vega, A. (2015). Opportunity for all: Three social Inclusion experiences in Peru's public libraries. *World Library and Information Congress*. <http://library.ifla.org/id/eprint/1179/7/165-talavera-en.pdf>
- Umoh, E. B., Habib, Z. S., & Yusuf, A. A. (2018). Role of public library in community development in Kano State. *International Journal of Operational Research in Management, Social Sciences and Education* 4 (1), 74 – 85. <http://www.internationalpolicybrief.org/images/2018/JULY/IJORMSSE/ARTICLE7.pdf>
- Identifying social inclusion and exclusion. *Leaving no one behind: The imperative of inclusive development. Report on the World Social Situation 2016*. <https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/rwss/2016/chapter1.pdf>
- Utor, J.K. & Utor, J.S. (2006). Information needs of rural communities in Vandeikya Local Government Area of Benue State. *A paper presented at 45th Nigerian Library Association Conference and Annual General Meeting*.
- Uzuegbu, C. P. & Uzuegbu, C. (2013). Community information centre services: A prospective pathway to national transformation and development in Nigeria. In A. O. Issa, K. N. Igwe & C. P. Uzuegbu (Eds), *Provision of Library and Information Services to Users in the Era of Globalisation* (pp.). Lagos, Nigeria: Waltodany Visual Concept.
- Wiyono, E. (2021). Library transformation based on social inclusion in accelerated COVID-19 pandemic treatment. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research, 564*. 192 – 194. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Administration Science 2020*. <https://www.atlantispress.com/article/125958397.pdf>
- Yadav, S. (2017). Information needs and information seeking behaviour of female workers in Lakhipur Tea Garden. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 22 (2), 37 -42. <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol.%2022%20Issue12/Version-2/F2212023742.pdf>